

The Influence of Digital Advertising on Consumer Purchasing Behavior Among Millennials in Southeast Asian Markets

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Abstract—Advertising is commonly used to foster sales and reputation of an institution. It is at first the growth of print advertising that has increased the population and number of periodicals of newspaper and its circulation. The rise of Internet and online media has somehow blurred the role of media and advertising though the intention is still to reach out to audience and to increase sales. The relationship between advertising and audience on a product purchase through persuasion has been developing from print media to online media. From the changing media environment and audience, it is the concern of this research to study the impact of online advertising to such a relationship cycle. The content of online advertisements is much of text, multimedia, photo, audio and video. The messages of such content format may indeed bring impacts to its audience and its credibility. This study is therefore reflecting the effectiveness of online advertisement and its influences on generation Y in their purchasing behavior. This study uses Media Dependency Theory to analyze the relationship between the impact of online advertisement and media usage pattern of generation Y. Hierarchy of Effectiveness Model is used as a marketing communication model to study the effectiveness of advertising and further to determine the impact of online advertisement on generation Y in their purchasing decision making. This research uses online survey to reach out the sample of generation Y. The results have shown that online advertisements do not affect much on purchase decision making even though generation Y relies much on the media content including online advertisement for its information and believing in its credibility. There are few other external factors that may interrupt the effectiveness of online advertising. The very obvious influence of purchasing behavior is actually derived from the peers.

I. INTRODUCTION

A

DVERTISING is an audio or visual form of marketing communication that employs an openly sponsored, non-personal message to promote or sell a product, service or idea [1]. The nature of advertising is to persuade its audience to purchase a product or service, though there is institutional advertising which seeks to build corporate reputation without appealing for sales [2].

Advertising does not appear on its own. It has been standing on the pillar of media from old Egyptian papyrus to the Millennium online media [3]. The key function of advertising is to get through its sales message to reach out its target audience and to further engage a purchasing process. In a broader view, advertising, which is one of the collective terms of marketing communication, aims to build a brand through various types of planned messages. Marketing communication

functions have little value without media where media is the vehicle through which promoting correspondence messages are conveyed to (and from) target groups of users. In the view of marketing communication, Duncan [4] has defined advertising as non-personal communication. Advertising is a paid announcement where it is sponsored by an identified sponsor. Duncan has further explained the use of advertising in reaching audiences. Other than that, advertising is used to build brand awareness and to differentiate a brand. Lastly, advertising may build an image for the brand.

In the perspective of general understanding of mass communication, advertisers are *senders*, with the goal, of sending product *messages* through mass *media*, to reach the *audience*. In such a cycle of relationship, the role of advertising has never been changed time. Advertising has been further advanced to another level of communications since the use of Internet. At a different form of transmission device from print to electronic then online media, and a different generation of audience, advertising effects might be differing. It is the media and target audience differing from time to time. The various types of mass media along the changes have been from newspapers, magazines and books to television and radio with the existence of print media, and thereafter from electronic media to online media at the presence of both print and electronic media [5]. As the rapid pace of information technology has evolved this changing environment and audience, it is the concern of this research to study the impact of online advertising in this causal relationship.

The rise of Internet and information technology has further advanced the content of online media and advertising. The strength of online media is where it allows text, multimedia effects, photo, audio and video. This new format has also allowed changes in the relationship between advertisers and target audience in communications, from traditional one-way to interactive communications. The new format with variety of content is somehow confusing its

audience and it may even reduce the credibility of its message. According to Tavor [6], a negative attitude may be imposed towards the brand and the advertisement when too many of times an advertisement appears. Somehow different Asian markets and different digital channels have shown different levels of credibility though Malaysia has shown higher level of trust in digital advertisements which include online advertisements [7].

Looking at the causal relationship of advertising, media and target audience, this research is to study the effectiveness of online advertisement and its influences on generation Y in their purchasing behavior. Generation Y is chosen as it is the generation of Internet and information technology. Generation Y is estimated with high direct and indirect purchasing power. Their purchasing power is even far greater than their parents ever have [8]. They are also the main target of advertisers as they can be easily influenced and they like to spend money on personal product [9].

Due to such characteristics of Generation Y, they are likely the target audience of online advertisements that advertisers aim to reach out to. This research is reflecting on the purchasing behavior of generation Y by following the model of marketing communication, Hierarchy of Effectiveness. As such this research is therefore implying the factors that may influence the purchase decision making among the generation with just a trend of paradigm shift or a permanent formation of behavior.

II. THE GROWTH OF GLOBAL ONLINE ADVERTISING VERSUS

MALAYSIAN ONLINE POPULATION AND SHOPPING BEHAVIOUR

Advertising has been developed into two major forms based on the nature of its media. There are mainly print and electronic advertising. The rise of Internet has overtaken print media while it has further advanced the development of electronic media and formed new media, namely online media in the digital age. The market of major publicity traded newspaper business in the United States has marked a decline by 42% in January 2004 to August 2008. It is recognized by Evans [10] that the newspapers are losing readers and advertisers to online media supported by online advertising. According to Evans, online advertising has become a significant source of revenue for web-based businesses as it is able to draw consumers directly to their web sites where they can browse and view online and purchase directly from the vendor within a few clicks.

Online advertising has been increasing over the years comparatively to other media. Online advertising market is growing gradually each year. There is increasing number of companies now allocating more marketing funds for online advertising. Referring to Global Online Advertising

Spending Statistics [11], such scenario is due to the reasons that online advertising track record is easier to be followed up; possibility of customized campaigns for targeted group; and, it is much easier to make changes for online campaigns. The report has also commended that the strength of online advertising has benefited both marketers and consumers. The bond between the two parties has been much developed through new media. Global online advertisement spending versus total advertisement spending, as in Table I, has reflected the growth of online advertising which is meant to support the bond of marketers and consumers.

TABLE I
GLOBAL ONLINE AD SPENDING VERSUS TOTAL AD SPENDING [11]

Year	2011	2012	2013
Total Advertisement Spending (USD/Billions)	496.9	529.5	552.5
Online Advertisement Spending (USD/Billions)	80.2	94.2	106.1

The gradual growth of global online advertisement spending is a remarkable indication to reflect the growth of online users who are potentially online shoppers and buyers.

The Internet penetration rate growth is closely tied to online marketing strategy and online businesses. According to Internet World Stats [12], in 2004 the number of subscribers was 2.9 million, in 2005 it increased to 3.5 million subscribers, and in 2006 the number of subscribers in Malaysia was close to 5 million. The growth of Malaysian online population has led to the boom of online shops. Due to the nature of young online viewers, who are connected through Internet, they have become the targets of advertisers who aim to sell their products and services to the young online viewers with the buying behavior which can be transmitted from traditional practices to online spending behavior. Therefore Malaysian buying behavior is to be reviewed to meet/understand the transmission of behavior.

Malaysians are keen researchers prior to purchase. 70% of Malaysians research before they purchase (be it online or offline), and this is one of the highest rates in Southeast Asia, more than Taiwan (69%), Korea (63%), China (59%), Singapore (54%), Japan (39%). According to Wong [13], there are 91% of Malaysian online users actually shop online. The same report has also indicated that there are 85% of online shoppers spend RM500 online or less in a month; the top three reasons of shopping online are to compare, to discover and lastly to be exclusive.

At this part of this research, Malaysian online population and Malaysian online shopping trend are set to the causal relationship with global online advertisement spending. It is to understand why online population may attract such a huge amount of online advertising spending to reach out to online target audience. This has also reflected the direct

impact of online advertising to lure online users to make the move to research online and further purchase the goods.

III. EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE ADVERTISEMENTS

Due to the changing role of online media, which has been commercialized, advertising has also followed its transformation moving into a new bandwagon of online advertising. According to Saleh [14], online advertising has been claimed effective where only 8% of internet users account for 85% of clicks on display advertisements. The average click rate for display advertisement campaign is 0.1% that only one in a thousand advertisements gets clicked. Saleh has also revealed that even though so the average click rate is, there are still, 95% of Google's revenue coming from online advertising. Looking at such an attractive revenue, there are many actions and strategies compiled to enhance the effectiveness of an online advertisement. At the same time, there are also many methods created to measure the effectiveness of advertisements in order to attract more advertisers.

The most common long standing method of measuring advertising effect is through AIDA, which is Attention, Interest, Desire and Action [15]. According to Karlsson [16], AIDA explains that an advertisement is first to raise awareness. It is then to stimuli the interest, to lead the consumers to their desires and it is eventually followed by the action of purchasing. Danaher and Mullarkey [17] further developed the elements of measuring the effectiveness of an advertisement by its advertisement recall, advertisement recognition, brand awareness, click through rate, attitude towards the advertisement and the brand, and lastly purchase consideration.

This research is particularly testing on two aspects in measuring effectiveness of advertising. The two aspects are ability to recall and attitude towards advertisements, in this context, it refers to online advertisements.

A. Ability of Recalling an Online Advertisement

Recall in measuring effectiveness of an advertisement refers to the cognition of a viewer on an advertisement. It means how a consumer responds to the information, learns and understands the message in the advertisement. The key concept about recalling is the after effects, where after the consumers see an advertisement, the consumers can remember the advertisement by tracing deeply with the cognitive response.

There are factors that may affect the recall on an advertisement. These factors are advertisement characteristics, Internet users' viewing mode and duration of viewing, campaign publicity, attitudes towards the web site or advertisement itself, and curiosity and innovative advertising strategy. Of these characteristics, duration and viewing mode are strong determinants of recall ability. However, online users under goal-directed viewing mode

are less likely to remember the advertisement than those surfing the site [18]. In some scenarios, online users' original activities have been disrupted and they are forced to watch those unwanted advertisements and it may implant a negative attitude towards the advertisement and brand. Therefore, the ability of a user to recall an advertisement is significantly depending on the user's viewing mode.

B. Attitudes towards Online Advertisements

Effectiveness of advertising depends on the users' receptiveness towards an advertisement and on their attitudes towards advertising [19]. Attitude towards an advertisement is the consumer's inclination to react to a particular message in a positive or negative manner. It has also been concluded that heavy online users hold strong beliefs about and attitudes towards online advertising which will be more likely leading to stronger purchase intent. On the other hand, online users will directly click to the intended article which they are interested in and they skip undesired information. This may result in less online advertising exposure and reduce the effectiveness of advertising [20].

This research studies mainly on these two areas in analyzing the effectiveness of online advertising.

IV. GENERATION Y IN THE PERSPECTIVE OF CONSUMERISM AND PURCHASE DECISION PROCESS

Generation Y consumers are also known as the Echo Boomer, iPod Generation and they are born during 1980s to 1990s [21]. More specifically, they are also accepted to be those born between years 1978 and 1994 [22]. This generation is a big market as it is the largest population than other generations. It is creating the markets which are not only for cars and gasoline, but also for music, entertainment, fast food, computer, cell phones and many other products. Generation Y consumers seem to be more preferable to spend on personal care product than others. Teenagers currently spend over USD 150 billion annually for personal consumption.

In Malaysia, there are 11 millions of people accounted from Generation Y in 2010 when the total population of Malaysia is 28.6 million. Online purchase in Malaysia has reached its transactions worth RM 1.8 billion in 2011 with an estimation of 1.1 million online shoppers [23].

Looking at such a big number of online shoppers and some are potentially from Generation Y, the consumer behavior and its mapping into the process of purchase decision making are picked in this research.

A. Consumer Behavior of Generation Y

Kuester [24] has defined consumer behavior as the study of individuals in the processes to choose, secure, utilize, and discard items, administrations, encounters, or thoughts to fulfill needs and wants. Generation Y are generally grown up

in a consumption-driven society. They have more money at their disposal than any teen group in history [25]. As consumers, Generation Y demonstrates a general liking towards purchasing; they have ample discretionary time for shopping; and they have a tendency to spend money freely and quickly [26].

Generation Y consumers like to be the top of the trend and be accepted by their peers. Generation Y are image-driven and make personal statements with their image. Once the Millennial do make their choices in products and services, they expect transformed features in customization and personalization. The features are to meet their changes in needs, interests and tastes. Therefore, they seem more likely on purchasing products in order to build their image and acceptance from their peers [27]. More than that, Generation Y sees a reputable brand as an indicator of one's status and they are willing to pay extra for a preferred reputable brand [28]. It can be concluded in this part that, Generation Y is more likely to purchase on the product which fulfills their needs of esteem and self-actualization. Generation Y has a strong need to belong to but are in some respects far more concerned with issues of esteem and self-actualization [29]. The needs for esteem refer to the needs of a stable, firmly based, high level of self-respect and respect from others. When these needs are satisfied, the person will feel selfconfident and valuable as a person in the world [30].

In view to such behavior of generation Y consumers they are much targeted by online and offline marketers.

B. Process of Purchase Decision Making

Consumer decision making refers to the result of buying and using the goods and services. The process of purchase involves stages to reach the final stage of purchasing.

The first step, Need Recognition, refers to the consumer's need (or problem). It occurs when an individual detects between what an ideal and actual affair is. It leads to need recognition which prolongs to a stage of information searching in order to find a solution for the unmet needs. Information searching stage is to get data to make a decision.

Third process of pre-purchase search refers to the action of consumers making product and brand comparison. It is to narrow down alternatives before final purchase. The last process is the evaluation of alternatives. Based on memory, the consumer uses the preexisting evaluations to select products, services, brands. If the person is satisfied with the product choices, he or she will proceed to purchase and consumption [31]. When this process is mapped to the behavior of Generation Y, it is noticed that the generation takes more time in information searching and it is more difficult for them to decide on the purchase. Generation Y spends much more time by requiring and analyzing about a product or a service [32]. The choice on retailers is rather

careful and rational which indicates a low loyalty level to the retailer [33]. During the process of information searching and analyzing, reviews of former customers are very significant to them. These reviews are commonly placed on Facebook or producers' own websites [34].

This research is therefore studying the behavior and purchase decision of Generation Y through the mapping of the process of purchase decision making. It is to find out the factors that impact them more along the process.

V. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. Media Dependency Theory

Media Dependency Theory is about how much an individual depends on the media to fulfill his or her needs. In this respect, there is a relationship between the media, audience and the social system. Firstly, media attracts individuals with the content which is able to fulfill the audience's needs for understanding, entertainment, and information. This will grow the strength in dependence relationship. Therefore, the users realize the importance of media to them in the cognitive level. The individuals in such a stage are to stay on its attention motivation brought by the media which will increase a user's level of satisfaction. Eventually the audience is put to a higher level of involvement in the process of information [35]. In short, it refers to an idea of the relationship between media use and its role in media users' lives and eventually the influences they have. People who depend more on the media, a more noticeable measure of the media's impacts will be on that person. Not every people will be influenced by the media, it depends on how much that person relies on the media. The degree of audience dependence on media information is the key variable in understanding when and why media message alter audience beliefs, feelings or behavior [36].

This research is using this theory to study the use of online media among Generation Y, where the more the generation relies on Internet; there are more effects on them. This theory is also to reflect on the impact of online advertising on Generation Y that the more the generation is exposed to online advertisements the more they are led to purchase the product. Thus this theory is perceived that it is able to explain such a relationship cycle among the variables mentioned.

B. Hierarchy of Effects Model

Bovee et al. [37] have defined the model as to assume of people learning about something from advertising, further developing feelings towards the product, asking about the product and finally they act on it. Advertising drives consumers through the six steps from unawareness to reach ultimate purchase. The steps are awareness, knowledge, liking, preference, conviction and purchase. However, these steps are related to three main behavioral dimensions;

cognitive, affective and conative. The cognitive component indicates awareness and knowledge; the affective component indicates liking and preference; and, the conative (or motivational) component indicates conviction and purchase [38]. If a person is aware of an advertisement, the person will start to get to know more information about the advertisement. When the person is liking the product, the person will start seeking or comparing the alternative of the choices. Lastly purchasing will be made. This is the one reason that we need to know about the sequential hierarchy of effects in advertising [39].

In this research, Hierarchy of Effective Model is used to measure the effectiveness of online advertising as it explains how the advertisements affect Generation Y in purchase decision. It also explains how the effectiveness of an online advertisement is and it depends on how Generation Y responds to the advertisement which is able to grab their attention firstly.

This research is conformed to Hierarchy of Effective Model which is able to measure the effectiveness of online advertising towards Generation Y. Based on the model, it helps to explain and predict the behavior of Generation Y in purchase decision making.

VI. METHODOLOGY

This research studies on the impact of online advertising on Generation Y's purchase decision in Malaysia. An analytical survey is conducted to examine the interrelationships among the variables which are the impact of online advertising, Generation Y and purchase decision making.

The survey is conducted in an online manner. A sample of 100 respondents who are online users aged between 23 and 33 years old are targeted as the research sample. The gender of respondents is equally distributed in this research.

The survey progression has started in January 2014 and ended in March 2014. Once the survey progression ends, the researchers start to tabulate all responses that are collected from the respondents and determine the results for further analysis.

VII. DATA ANALYSIS

Survey results are analyzed based on the four parts as in the questionnaires. It is to be presented in the form of tables and text. The snowball sampling is up to 100, which indicates a respondent number and percentage of 100 as well.

The respondents of this research are all from the categories of Generation Y. They are all Malaysians. Though gender is not the key issue, the researchers manage to distribute the equal share of respondents in gender.

A. Demography

The demographic profile of the respondents of this research is shown in Table I. As the respondent number is 100, in this context, the frequency is equivalent to its percentage.

The respondents are aged ranging from 18 to 32 years old. There are 43% of the respondents from the group of students, 48% from the working group and 9% are unemployed. Among the working group and students who are working either full time or part time, 69% of them are earning less than RM2000 per month. 31% of them are earning at RM2000 and above. The respondents are mostly from urban area of the country.

TABLE II
RESPONDENTS' DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE
Elements

		9
		22
of you surfing online? (Please tick only one answer that best describes your purpose)	Socialization Relaxing Education purpose Entertainment Other, please specify _____	32 13 13 5 0

B. Patterns of Media Consumption

This part of data shows the media preference and the weekly frequency usage of Internet among Generation Y. The data show that almost all of the Generation Y used

Internet as their main medium whereas only 1% out of 100 respondents uses television more frequently. 6% of respondents claimed that they use newspaper and radio more frequently.

The result proves that Generation Y is still remaining on Internet as their main medium. It may be due to the reason that they are born and brought up in the technology world. They seem to rely on Internet as they spend time on Internet almost every day. Besides, they seldom spend time on the traditional main media such as television, newspaper and radio. This is because Internet is more convenient to them as they can get news easily from the web and they could connect with their friends instantly. At this point, online advertisement is relatively seen to be more effective to them compare to a print advertisement.

90% of respondents claim that they use Internet every day in a week, while 6% respondents use Internet for three to four times in a week. Only 4% of respondents spend time on Internet for five to six times in a week. Therefore, it can indicate that most of the Generation Y use Internet every day. The daily Internet usage among Generation Y is 4-6 hours per day. 24 out of 50 male respondents spend slightly more than female respondents as only 16 female respondents engage on internet 4-6 hours per day. 22 of female respondents in total indicate that they only spend about 1 to 3 hours online daily or even lesser. Female respondents are light users compared to male respondents. 17 male respondents indicated that they use Internet for 7 hours and above.

Throughout the survey, male respondents stand at the highest frequency of using Internet compared to female respondents. As shown in Table III, the highest number of respondents, 37 out of 100, use Internet for news and information purpose. The second highest amount, 32 out of 100, claims that they use internet for socialization purpose. Only 31 of them go online for the purposes of relaxing, education and entertainment.

The data have shown that most of the generation Y use Internet to get the real time news and information to satisfy their need of information. It also shows that generation Y are more likely to use Internet to socialize with their friends.

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C. The Effectiveness of Online Advertisements

The preference of receiving information from the types of media among Generation Y may help enhance the possible effectiveness of online advertising. 41% of the respondents reflected that Internet is their preferred media to receive advertisement information from.

Of the advertisement information, 12 of the respondents may remember all of the information. 32% may remember

half and 28% may recall partial or some of the information. 21% of the respondents may remember little of the information and 7% of them will never remember the information.

The result also shows that almost half of the respondents ‘seldom’ click on the online advertisement for further details. 17 of them never click on the online advertisement and it is slightly higher than the respondents who choose ‘Always’ and ‘Often’. 25 out of 100 respondents claim ‘sometimes’.

The following data reflect on the level of online advertising’s effectiveness to the sample of Generation Y. The data have been simplified into Table IV where in the form of Likert scale, 1 being strongly agree and 5 being strongly disagree.

Table IV shows that online advertisement is necessary to the respondents and they also think that online advertisement information is credible and attractive enough. 51% of the respondents agree to the statement while only 18% of respondents disagree that online advertisement is necessary for them. Besides, 62% of the respondents agree that the online advertisement info is credible and attractive to them. It indicates that the online advertisement information is more credible and attractive than a print advertisement for Generation Y.

As of the opinion of Generation Y on whether they will click through the online advertisements which drive their interest first rather than their needs towards the product, there are 68 of them agree to the statement. There are only 13 of them will click on and be aware of the online advertisement if they are free to surf online during their entertainment time. At the same time 62 of them agree that they are more likely to remember the online advertisement if the advertisement is offbeat and attractive to them. Besides that, 43 out of 100 respondents will remember an online advertisement if the advertisement contains a dominant endorser. In contrary, only 26 respondents disagree that the dominant endorser will affect them to remember an online advertisement.

TABLE IV
THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE ADVERTISEMENT

No	Statements	1 2 3 4 5				
		(%)				
C4.	I think online advertisement is necessary.	11	40	31	13	5
C5.	I think that the product information in online advertisement is credible and attractive.	10	52	31	5	2
C6	I will click on the online advertisement if the advertisement has driven my interest first rather than my need towards the product.	15	53	22	8	2
C7.	I will click on and be aware of the online advertisement if I am free to surf online during my entertainment time.	2	11	24	35	28

C8.	I will remember the online advertisement if the online advertisement is offbeat and attractive.	12	50	22	11	5
C9.	I will remember the online advertisement if there is a dominant endorser inside the advertisement.	4	39	31	24	2
C10.	I would like to expose myself to online advertisement rather than print advertisement.	7	22	47	18	6

Majority of the respondents agreed that online ad is necessary, credible and attractive, but they are neutral when they are asked about whether they would like to expose themselves to an online advertisement. In this respect, only 29 of them would like to expose themselves to online advertisement rather than print advertisement.

D. Purchase Decision Making Process

The frequency of online advertisements may influence Generation Y to do purchase on the particular product and may be an element to the purchase decision making process. Throughout the research, the result shows that 36 out of 100 respondents sometimes do purchase based on the online advertisement. ‘Seldom’ and ‘never’ take an equal amount of respondents about the influence of online advertisements.

The level of influence has been simplified into Table V. Table V is to make easy understanding on the impact of online advertisements to the purchase decision making of Generation Y.

TABLE V
PURCHASE DECISION MAKING

No	Statement	1 2 3 4 5				
		(%)				
D2.	I will search the product information through online before I do my purchase decision.	32	47	13	6	2
D3.	I will be more likely to read newspaper or magazine to get the product information.	2	9	27	42	20
D4.	Online advertisement influences me to search more about the product information immediately.	10	35	23	16	16
D5.	Online advertisement influences me to compare the product to other alternatives.	8	41	38	11	2
D6.	Online advertisement influences me to change my perception towards the product.	5	41	42	10	2
D7.	Online advertisement influences my purchase decision to the particular product.	6	30	22	39	3
D8.	Online advertisement influences me to try a new product or a new brand.	10	26	29	31	4
D9.	I will make my purchase decision based on <i>Word Of Mouth</i> (friends, family and peers) rather than online advertisement.	22	52	18	8	0
D10.	I will make my purchase decision based on bloggers’ reviews on the product.	3	14	33	31	19

Referring to Table V, 79% of them agree that they will search the product information through online before they make the purchase decision. Only 8% of the respondents do

not search the product information online before they purchase. It can be concluded that majority of the respondents will search the product information online before they do any purchase and they will see the online advertisements when they do the research. However, the online advertisement did not influence them to purchase. Comparatively to print media, only 11% of the respondents get product information from the source of print media.

There are few other factors that may influence the respondents’ purchase decision-making other than online advertisements. Other factors referred are product research, comparison, perception change, purchasing and to try a new product. Somehow online advertisement may prompt Generation Y to do more product information search that 45% of the respondents agree on this view. Other than that, 49% of the respondents agree that online advertisement influences them to compare the product to other alternatives. 54% of the respondents claim neutral and disagreed that online advertisements may influence them on perception change. However, 36% of them are influenced by online advertisements to do purchasing. Furthermore, 35% of the respondents also indicate that online advertisements do not affect them to try a new product. It explains that online advertisements do not influence Generation Y’s perception as well as purchasing decision.

Throughout the finding, the result indicates that online advertisement is able to influence Generation Y to do product research immediately. Besides, online advertisements are able to influence Generation Y to do comparison through online. However, an online advertisement does not influence Generation Y in their perception and purchase.

Table V has shown that the external factors like influence of friends, family and peer may affect Generation Y in their purchase decision. Only 8 out of 100 respondents will not be influenced by their peers’ opinion.

Overall, most of the Generation Y is the opinion follower. They will follow their opinion leader’s idea, pattern and opinion. This can prove that Generation Y is image-driven and they like to connect with their peers by purchasing a new product of their view. They are somehow not influenced by the reviews of bloggers online.

VIII. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that Generation Y probably remember advertisements that pull to their advantage. They tend to click on an online advertisement based on their interest rather than their need towards the product. Besides, dominant endorser is a factor that attracts Generation Y’s attention to the online advertisement as Generation Y like to follow the trends of their stars, idols and peers’ in order to be connected with them. Generation Y listen to their peers’ opinions in choosing a product. In

their purchasing pattern, Generation Y are more likely to follow their peer group's influence but there are some can be influenced by the online advertisement and lead them to try a new product. Hence, the elements of an online advertisement can be significantly getting their attention and they will want to get more details about the product.

Generation Y generally use Internet mainly for news and information and socialization purposes. Secondary use of Internet among Generation Y would be for leisure, entertainment and education.

In terms of Media Dependency Theory, though Generation Y are heavy users, its media effects are only influencing the generation to search product information more thoroughly. It is also helping the generation make product comparison easily within clicks. In par with Hierarchy of Effects, the impact of advertising is to create awareness and product information search.

Online advertising has proven its exposure to Generation Y by creating awareness and information search. It does not trigger them in their purchasing behavior. Other external factors like words of mouth, family and peers are the ultimate impact on their purchase decision making.

APPENDIX

Yes, I agree to participate in this survey.

Instruction: Respondents are to tick (√) only an answer until that special request is stated.

Part A- Demography

This part is structured into Table VI with a few questions enquiring on personal particulars from the respondents.

TABLE VI
DEMOGRAPHY

Please tick (√) the answer for the following questions. Only ONE tick for each question.

- Gender:
- A1. Female
 Male
- Age:
- A2. 18-22
 23-27
 28-32
 33 and above
- Employment status:
- A3. Working
 Unemployed
 Student
- Income:
- A4. Less than RM2000
 RM2000- RM2999
 RM3000-RM3999

Other, please specify _____

- A5. Which of the following best describes the area you live in?
 Urban area
 Sub-urban area
 Rural area

Part B – Patterns of Media Consumption

This part is structured into Table VII with a few questions enquiring on the behavior of media consumption in forming a pattern of it among the respondents.

PATTERNS OF MEDIA CONSUMPTION Please tick (√) the answer for the following questions. Only ONE tick for each question.

What type of media do you often use?

- Newspaper
 Radio

B1.

- Television
 Online
 Other, please specify _____ How frequent in a week you go online?

- 1-2 times
 3-4 times

B2.

- 5- 6 times
 Everyday
 Other, Please specify _____

How long do you spend your time online per day?

- Less than 1 hour
 1-3 hours

B3.

- 4-6 hours
 7-9 hours
 10 hours and above

What is the main purpose of you surfing online? (Please tick only one answer that best describes your purpose)

- News and Information
 Socialization

B4.

- Relaxing

- () Education
- () Other, please specify _____

Part C – The Effectiveness of Online Advertisements

This part is structured into Table VIII with a few questions about your perception of online advertisement and its influences on your daily life.

TABLE VIII
THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE ADVERTISEMENTS

question: tick (✓) the answer for the following questions.

TABLEVII Only ONE tick for each

- C1. Which media do you prefer to receive advertisement information?
 - () Print
 - () Television
 - () Radio
 - () Mobile
 - () Internet
 - () Other, please specify _____
- C2. How much can you remember the information that you have seen or read from online advertisements?
 - () Almost all of the information
 - () Half of the information
 - () Partially/ some of the information
 - () Little of the information
 - () Never remember

When an online advertisement appears or pops up, how frequent would you click on it for further details?

 - () Always
 - () Seldom
 - () Never

purpose () entertainment

Please read each of the statement and tick (✓) in the box provided to indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the statement.

(1= Strongly Agree, 2 = Agree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Disagree, 5 = Strongly Disagree)

No	Statements	1	2	3	4	5
C4.	I think online advertisement is necessary.					
C5.	I think that the product information in online advertisement is credible and attractive.					
C6	I will click on the online advertisement if the advertisement has driven my interest first rather than my need towards the product.					
C7.	I will click on and be aware of the online advertisement if I am free to surf online during my entertainment time.					
C8.	I will remember the online advertisement if the online advertisement is offbeat and attractive.					
C9.	I will remember the online advertisement if there is a dominant endorser inside the advertisement.					
C10.	I would like to expose myself to online advertisement rather than print advertisement.					

Part D – Purchase Decision Making Process

Below are the questions about your purchase decision making pattern.

TABLE IX
PURCHASE DECISION MAKING PROCESS

Please tick (✓) the answer for the following questions. Only ONE tick for each question.

- D1. How often an online advertisement influences you in purchasing?
 - () Always
 - () Often
 - () Sometimes
 - () Seldom
 - () Never

Below are the statements about how online advertisement influences your purchase decision in your daily life. Please read each of the statement and tick (✓) in the box provided to indicate to what extent that you agreed or disagreed with the statement.

(1= Strongly Agree, 2 = Agree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Disagree, 5 = Strongly Disagree)

No	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
D2.	I will search the product information through online before I do my purchase decision.					
D3.	I will be more likely to read newspaper or magazine to get the product information.					

- () Seldom
- () Never

Below are the statements to measure the level of influence by online advertisement in your daily life.

- D4. Online advertisement influences me to search more about the product information immediately.
- D5. Online advertisement influences me to compare the product to other alternatives.
- D6. Online advertisement influences me to change my perception towards the product.
- D7. Online advertisement influences my purchase decision to the particular product.
- D8. Online advertisement influences me to try a new product or a new brand.
- D9. I will make my purchase decision based on *Word Of Mouth* (friends, family and peers) rather than online advertisement.
- D10. I will make my purchase decision based on bloggers' reviews on the product.

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